

Early interaction, communication and autism

Early interaction, communication and the origins of autism:

Far-reaching insights by Ángel Rivière

(Interacción temprana, comunicación y los orígenes del autismo:

La visión con largo alcance de Ángel Rivière)

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Abstract:

In this paper we revisit some ideas of the early work by Ángel Rivière that not only marked his later research but anticipated an approach that, in essence, is still valid and reflects current advances in our understanding of autism as a developmental condition primarily affecting social interaction and communication. More specifically we focus on how: (1) his insights on the possible alteration on early interaction programs of infant/adult communication both determined his own later research and preceded evidence impossible to obtain at the time; (2) his view on the early symbolization at the end of infancy shaped an incipient approach that identified a key semiotic dimension for the diagnosis and intervention in autism; (3) his early constructivist model integrated the best of the Piagetian and Vygostkian constructivisms and is still compatible with the modern neuroconstructivism, balancing the input of 'nature and nurture' in the study of communication and its neurodevelopmental disorders.

Key words: Autism, early social interaction, symbols, development, socio-constructivism, Ángel Rivière

Resumen:

En este artículo recuperamos algunas de las ideas de los primeros trabajos de Ángel Rivière que, no sólo determinaron su investigación posterior, sino que anticiparon una perspectiva que en esencia es aún válida y que refleja algunos de los conocimientos actuales en nuestra comprensión del autismo como una condición del desarrollo que afecta primordialmente a la interacción social y la comunicación. En concreto nos centraremos en cómo: (1) sus intuiciones sobre la posible alteración de los programas de interacción temprana de la comunicación entre bebé/adulto determinaron tanto su propia investigación posterior como precedieron parte de la evidencia imposible de obtener en aquel momento; (2) su manera de entender la simbolización al final de la primera infancia dio forma a una incipiente propuesta clínica que planteaba una dimensión semiótica para el diagnóstico y la intervención en autismo; (3) su primer modelo constructivista integraba lo mejor de los constructivismos piagetiano y vygostkiano y es compatible con el neuroconstructivismo actual,

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equilibrando el peso de la ecuación “naturaleza y crianza” en el estudio de la comunicación y los trastornos del neurodesarrollo.

Palabras clave: Autismo, interacción social primaria, símbolos, desarrollo, socio-constructivismo, Ángel Rivière

Interaction and symbol in autism

In 1983, very early in his career, Ángel Rivière published a key paper — “Interaction and symbol in Autism”—in which he proposed that autism was best understood as an alteration of social cognitive development. His proposal was based, on the one hand, on an exciting new wave of studies on early social cognitive abilities of infants during their first year of life, and on the other, on his profound knowledge of the main theories in developmental psychology —Piaget’s individual and Vygotsky’s social constructivisms. This allowed him to discern and distil the profound implications of those exciting new works with infants, not only for autism but for developmental psychology in general. Here, we revisit the key ideas of that paper and how it marked Rivière’s later work and anticipated an approach whose key outlines are still valid and reflect current cutting-edge advances in our understanding of autism as a developmental condition primarily affecting social interaction and communication.

Infant Communication and Autism

In his paper Rivière captured a pivotal moment in the study of autism. The study of early social interaction and communication in typical infants during their first year of life had just started, with the pioneering works of Bruner, Ryan, Sugarman, Trevarthen and Bates (among others) just published during the second half of the 1970s. Infant developmental psychology had been dominated by the study of physical knowledge in the spirit of Piagetian sensorimotor intelligence —object permanence, tool use, etc— and even the emerging challenges to Piaget’s theory occurred mainly in the traditional Piagetian domain of physical intelligence (e.g., Bower, 1974) (see Gómez, 2004). In the 70s, however, a new strand of works focused on infants as developing social beings growing up in a social world, had started to appear. These pioneering studies reported a repertoire

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of social sensitivity and responses of unsuspected sophistication and complexity. Rivière immediately realised the transforming potential that these studies had for understanding autism in its ‘pathognomic’ essence (that “inability to relate to people” that Kanner placed at the core of the syndrome in 1943). Those studies illustrated the sort of early social competence whose impairment might explain Autism.

Rivière’s proposal was that the origins of autism must lie in alterations in those early patterns of social interaction that start at birth, grow in complexity and scope during the first months of life, and culminate (first) with the appearance of prelinguistic intentional communication at the end of the first year of life, and (eventually) with the production of symbolic communication and meaning at the end of infancy. The implications of any alteration in these patterns are potentially enormous because, from a Vygotskian perspective, they can affect the whole of cognitive development, not only its social side.

At the time that Rivière wrote his paper, however, it was impossible to ascertain what exactly was wrong in the first year of life of a child with Autism, what alterations prevented them from taking the typical developmental path. In 1983, it was impossible to know this directly because Autism could only be diagnosed in the preschool years at the earliest (and often, much later). Evidence that is available today -thanks to the prospective studies with babies at high risk of developing autism¹- was not even imaginable. Rivière’s paper was therefore largely theoretical and hypothetical; his insights were, nevertheless, rightly informed not only by his profound knowledge of developmental psychology and his eagle-eyed view on the implications of the findings on infant’s studies but also by his own clinical practice.

In a nutshell, Rivière’s story was the following. Early social development in infants is characterised by two types of mechanisms or programs —*attunement* programs, that direct and connect infants

¹ Studies that look at the developmental trajectories of siblings of children with autism (high risk) and compare them with those of siblings of children with typical development (low risk)

Early interaction, communication and autism with their caregivers, and *harmonisation* programs, that allow them to respond and enter into reciprocal, coordinated interaction with others from the beginning of life. For example, babies are preferentially attracted to human voices (attunement), and they respond to vocal (normally also facial) expressive addresses with synchronized vocal responses structured in turn-taking bouts, known as protoconversations² (harmonization). In this way, typical infants are integrated into a dynamic interpersonal system that drives and structures their development³.

The infant with autism —Rivière deduced— must fail to build some of these programs; for example, they may not attend to the key social features of people, such as their faces or their voices, and they may have some severe impairments in programs for early interaction, such as action synchronization or protoconversations. These alterations would have consequences for later development, preventing them from experiencing the key transition into triadic patterns of interaction (sharing attention and action upon objects) where prelinguistic intentional communication emerges in the form of *protoimperatives* and *protodeclaratives* (now referring to Bates's 1979 seminal terms). With these early forms of referential communication, infants pursue their goals about objects by intentionally recruiting other people's help, or recruit other people's attention to share their interest in objects. This is achieved through specialised behaviours such as pointing gestures, eye-contact, and gaze following organised in coordinated units of social *interaction* (that later on often appeared in the developmental literature as units of "joint attention"). The absence or severe limitation of some of these advanced communicative behaviours (e.g. in the initiation of joint attention) was one of the tell-tale signs that led to a diagnosis of autism at 3 years of age (see e.g. Charman et al, 2001, Mundy, 2016). Most likely, they were never developed, and most likely their absence could be traced back to alterations in those earlier precursor patterns if only we could observe the development of children with autism during their first year of life.

² Using Trevarthen's (1979) expression

³ The description of these mechanisms and programs was further developed in two other key papers by Rivière in 1984 and in 1987 (in his paper with Coll) (see references).

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Much of Rivière's own later work is already anticipated in this paper, in two different aspects: (1) the role of early intentional communication as a precursor of theory of mind and (2) the role of the early symbols and the symbolization mechanisms rooted in interaction in the construction of meaning.

Intentional Communication as a precursor of the Theory of mind deficit in Autism

Shortly after the publication of Rivière's key paper, the Theory of Mind field was about to explode with the publication of the epoch-making paper by Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith (1985) *Does the autistic child have a theory of mind?* This paper presented a specific deficit in theory of mind as the core, domain-specific cognitive impairment to explain autism. Rivière's own research trajectory followed then a smooth integration of the early social cognitive competences with the new field of Theory of mind⁴. His own empirical studies with Sarriá showed that (in typically developing one-year-old infants) the intentional communication behaviours (those coordinated units of social *interaction*) were not related to the non-communicative intentional actions in the Piagetian sense (Sarriá and Rivière, 1991). A later study with Canal showed that children with autism present specific deficits in intentional communication in natural interactions with adults (Canal & Rivière, 1993). Results of these empirical studies suggested the existence of *specific* mechanisms for the socio-cognitive domain in typical development that were not present in the communication of children with autism. In this sense, early communication, especially early intentional communication, could be seen as the first, precursory steps in the development of that key ability which is theory of mind and which alteration seemed to capture so much of the essence of autism. Rivière's own research focused during the 90's on the fast-growing field of theory of mind and was led by the main theories (see e.g., Rivière & Núñez, 1996). Later on, he moved into a concept that linked such precursors of the human's interpersonal skills back to communication through "semiotic suspension" as a developmental system in the creation of meaning

⁴ See Sarriá & Gómez (2007) monograph in this journal.

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Symbols, Interaction and Semiotic Suspension

Rivière's idea on the "semiotic suspension" as the mechanisms of meaning and symbolization is strongly rooted in his 1983 paper. Rivière's notion was that the first symbols produced by children not only emerge from interaction but are themselves *evolved* forms of interaction derived from those contexts (from the exercise of those harmonization programmes). "Semiotic Suspension" provides the basic mechanism to create signifiers and acquires increasingly complex forms across development. In its early manifestations suspension "deprives" an action of both its original function and its complete topography in order to adopt a new form that imbues the signifier with a new function and creates new meaning. The growing complex levels in which this mechanism develops provide human communication with increasingly new possibilities towards: (1) semiotic reference, (2) functional autonomy of the signifiers and (3) expressive power of the representational systems (see Rivière, 1998; Rivière & Español, 2003; Rivière & Sotillo, 1999). Rivière proposes that the very same mechanism, at different levels of complexity, underlies all forms of symbolic production, from the early, enactive symbols of toddlers to the artistic expression in poetry, metaphors or even the abstraction process in any artistic creative process. More importantly, for the understanding of autism these different levels of suspension can be utilized to identify different levels of impairment in the development of autistic communication and, eventually, make use of this dimension also in tailored designed interventions. Sadly, Rivière's untimely death left only the outlined structure of what he envisaged as a new dimensional approach to diagnosis and intervention⁵ (the IDEA, *Inventario del Espectro Autista*, Rivière, 1998; 2000) in which the semiotic dimension was a key part.

Interaction and symbol today

Today we count with a wealth of direct data on the first year of life in Autism. A number of prospective, longitudinal studies that compare the developmental trajectories of children at high risk

⁵ In this respect he also anticipated, within the field of Autism, a dimensional rather than categorical approach; currently, a dimensional approach to mental health in general is becoming the main stream approach through the Research Domain [Criteria \(RDoC\)](#) (see Campos, Nieto y Núñez 2018).

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Early interaction, communication and autism of autism (siblings of an older brother or sister with ASD) with those of children at low risk (siblings of typically developing children) are showing us a picture that was unimaginable at the time of Rivière's key paper. And the fact is that Rivière's original predictions and ideas have fared astonishingly well capturing the essence of current cutting edge research on the social developmental nature of autism.

Consider, for example, the work of the Yale group, led by Amy Klin and Warren Jones. They were pioneers in reporting alterations in visual attention to social cues in high functioning adults with autism, who showed preferential attention to the mouth over the eyes area of faces (Klin *et al.*, 2002). They then replicated these findings in 2-year-old toddlers with early autism diagnosis, who paid preferential attention to mouths over eyes when looking at videos of people addressing them (Klin *et al.*, 2008). In their recent work, through prospective investigation of infants at risk of developing autism, they tried to track the origins of this altered social attention to the first months of life. To their surprise they did not find the predicted lack of tuning to the eyes of others from the beginning of life, but typical eye attention during the first 6 months, with the decline starting only after then (Jones & Klin, 2013). This finding was unexpected and in apparent contradiction with their cascading effects developmental model, according to which lack of attention to key social cues derails the development of social cognition in autism.

If attention to the right cues is intact at the beginning, something else must derail the development in autism. Here Rivière's notion of programs of *attunement* to the social world having to run in coordination with programs of *harmonisation* may come to the rescue. It is not enough to attend to the right thing, one must also respond to it in particular ways to enter into the social developmental process. The reason why attention to the eyes eventually declines in infants with autism might be that it is not sustained by coordinated mechanisms of social interaction conferring 'social meaning' to the eyes. Attending to the eyes is only a first step—the key is what else do infants do or fail to do once this visual orientation has been achieved? Indeed Schulz, Klin and Jones (2018), in a revised theoretical formulation to address some of their unexpected results, propose something uncannily

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similar to the model sketched by Rivière in 1983. They emphasise the importance of considering both early social *attention* and early social *interaction* mechanisms (attunement and harmonisation in Rivière's terminology), essentially reproducing, with the benefit of the plethora of behavioural, cognitive and physiological studies accumulated during the last decades, the 'developmental plot' that Rivière had already guessed from the first manifestations of the emerging field of early social interaction.

The attunement+harmonization (or Attention+ Interaction) approach, however, may not be as straightforward as presented in these formulations. Recently, prospective studies on infants at risk of autism from other groups not only fail to find early (before the 6th month of life) socio-cognitive markers in the attention (attunement) programs (see e.g., Elsabbagh and Johnson, 2016) but also, apparently, in the early interactions (harmonization) (e.g., Wan *et al*, 2012; Wan, Green and Scott, 2019). Although it is still early days to draw firm conclusions, this seems to indicate that the epigenesis of autism (and of typical development) is more intricate and multifaceted than captured by current socio-constructivist models and research methods, and that the key alterations may not (at least not yet) be traceable to the very beginnings of communicative development, as both Rivière's and the Yale group proposals assume. This does not invalidate the general approach to the constructivist role of interaction in both typical and atypical development, but forces us to reconsider it.

Reconsidering the socio-constructivist model: A universal, single developmental pathway?

One challenge that socio-constructivist theories need to address, and may help reformulating them, is the range of cross-cultural variation reported in early social interaction practices. Several cultures are characterized as not engaging with their infants in significant face to face interaction of the type so common in Western cultures. In some Non-Western cultures there are no "protoconversations," or dyadic turn-taking in face-to-face interactions. However, by the end of the first year of life, the essential components of intentional prelinguistic communication seem to be present in all cultures (Demuth, 2015).

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One possibility is that in these cultures the mutual attunement and harmonization mechanisms can follow different pathways, for example through interactions that are less visually mediated and rely more on other senses and the combination of them (e.g., tactual and/or auditory modalities). Indeed one limitation of interactionist models (and of the way socio-cognitive mechanisms have been studied in infancy in general) is that they have focused mainly on the visual aspects of social interactions. For example, Klin's group emphasises the cascading long-term effects that small alterations in preferential attention to the eyes may have on development. There is, however, compelling evidence of the resilience of developmental mechanisms in finding developmental routes based on other senses but the visual. The most dramatic evidence of multisensory interactive strategies comes, paradoxically, from children with multisensory impairments (deafblind children); even if delayed, children who are deafblind show structurally-equivalent patterns of dyadic and triadic interactions when we look at their attunement and harmonization behaviours through other sensory modalities. For example, they show mutual touch that reproduce the pattern of mutual glance or, more importantly, the pattern of joint attention in a tactual modality (or in the combination of residual sensory input by any modality) (Núñez, 2014).

This can be interpreted as proof that the infants' predispositions are greater and more resilient than suggested in some interactionist models; it may also mean, however, that the interactionist models (and main stream developmental psychology in general) have been narrowly shaped by the most salient, typical aspects of the developmental trajectory, presenting one single pathway. The proposed pathway for early communication relies too heavily on visual input and distal interactions (e.g., pointing gestures), leaving aside the multisensory nature of human communication. This drawback of interactionist models also has implications in the understanding of what may cause autism's communication and socio-cognitive development to derail, in view of current evidence of altered multisensory integration in older children and adults with autism (see e.g. Stevenson *et al.*, 2014).

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Two more general conclusions can be drawn from the evidence challenging interactionist models.

The first is that only by looking at the atypical pathways in development we can avoid the risk of overlooking key aspects of development itself. That was Rivière's approach to the study of autism. The second conclusion is that development (both typical and atypical) does not necessarily proceed in a single, universal pathway but the construction of human mental processes is permeable to the organism interaction with specific influences of the developmental contexts. Crucially, these are also core principles of the modern approach to constructivism known as neuroconstructivism (see, p.e., Karmiloff-Smith, 1998; Karmiloff-Smith et al., 2018).

By looking at the multifaceted, complex network of interactions between the organism genetic prescriptions and the different contexts of development that build our mental processes (and the underpinning brain networks), neuroconstructivism has the theoretical tools to face the main challenge of traditional constructivism, namely, to find the right balance between flexibility and resilience of developmental outcomes and trajectories. As López (2015) points out, however, it is fair to say that research based on this model has often not looked specifically at social interaction itself. Fortunately, the research focus is changing, and an increasing number of prospective studies (based on this theoretical approach) are looking at early parent/child interactions (PCI) (see e.g., Wan, Green and Scott, 2019) and presenting PCI interactions as a promising early intervention context (see e.g. Green et al., 2015; Althoff et al, 2019). A good example comes from Rivière's closest academic legacy with a research project where his early socio-constructivist view and the neuroconstructivist model converge currently in a prospective, longitudinal study of children at risk of developing autism (see <http://traberitea.wixsite.com/traberitea>)⁶.

In sum, the far-reaching ideas and insights anticipated by Rivière in his 1983 paper are still at the cutting edge of current research and models on how autism may emerge. In essence, the framework

⁶ His influence on many other former students and collaborators goes, however, well beyond his immediate context in Madrid; Rivière's legacy is present in the work of many of us who have developed our careers in other academic contexts. His inspiring influence is also present in the clinical and educational practice in Spain and Latin America (see e.g., Valdez, 2019).

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and the road map that he sketched not only anticipated much of the empirical evidence accumulated over the last years, but also inspired a new generation of researchers that can now contribute, first-hand, to build upon and provide the evidence and conceptual reformulations that he could only begin to imagine thirty years ago.

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